

Open Access Journals Focussing on Epidemiology

A study based on the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)

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Abstract

This paper identifies and lists out the scholarly Open Access (OA) journals in the field of Epidemiology, the branch of science dealing with public health of the society, covered in the DOAJ. A total of 180 journals in the subject field, which were added in the DOAJ database during the period 2004-2020 are identified and listed. The characteristics such as sponsoring agency of the journals, languages in which contributions are published, country-wise distribution, annual growth of number of the journals in Epidemiology added in the DOAJ database and the peer review system followed are subjected to further analysis. The growth in annual addition of titles in the DOAJ database, wide geographical distribution of the publications, language coverage and the presence of leading agencies as sponsors / publishers of the journals, and stringent peer review policy are viewed as positive indicators of scholarly nature of the OA journals in the subject field and this in turn would help in building better health system in our society.

Keywords: Open Access Journals; Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ); Epidemiology.

1. Introduction

Open Access (OA) is a movement which makes papers in scholarly journals freely available on the internet (Lewis, 2012). It is assumed that scholarly papers which are the results of research carried out at the expense of public funds should be made accessible for public use without any further cost. If all such academic contributions are freely accessible on the internet, scholarly communication would be improved and scientific research gets accelerated (Abadal, 2013). OA makes the intellectual output of a researcher freely available to the people through internet (Lone et al, 2008). As a result the visibility of the papers

will be more, which in turn enhances the possibility of their getting more citations and gaining great scientific impact. This way OA is beneficial to the researchers as well as to the society. On the basis of the nature of accessibility there are mainly two different OA methods. Self-archiving on the web can be considered as Green OA and publishing articles in OA journals can be termed as Gold OA (Gargouri et al., 2012).

Epidemiology is described as “the basic science of public health” (Savitz et al, 1999). It is the study of the distribution and determinants of health-related states or events in specified

populations, and the application of this study to the control of health problems (Last, 2001). Empirical research in this field produces valuable information that can be used for boosting the public health. The present CoViD-19 pandemic situation makes the awareness about scholarly information resources on epidemiology all the more relevant. Therefore the authors attempt the compilation of the scholarly OA journals specialising in epidemiology and an analysis of their significant characteristics. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is used as the source of data.

2. Review of Literature

No study specifically on OA journals in the field of Epidemiology could be located during the time of review of literature. But there are several papers available on OA journals in different subject areas. Some of them are worth mentioning here. McCabe & Snyder (2004) reported a study on the economics of the OA journals in a working paper which was started to get attention. The new business model for journal article, OA was a great success in later years. In the same year McVeigh (2004) also conducted a study in his book on the influence of Open Access journals in ISI citation database. The study revealed that there were an increasing number of OA journals in Web of Science database and the number keeps on growing. Since they can be accessed freely, their contents get cited more frequently.

A study on the citation impact of OA journals in Library and information Science (LIS) was made by Turk (2008) and pointed that the field also depicts the same pattern of increasing citation count of OA journal articles. Since the OA journals are becoming more and more popular and the growth in both number and quality necessitates innovations and constant up-gradation. Björk (2011) identified and explained some of the new techniques in the field of OA journal publishing. It described the developments like innovations in peer review techniques, new formats of journal articles and recent interactive media formats. The study concluded that the acceptance of OA

journals increasing day by day. So up-gradations and innovations are inevitable in this field.

Some studies were also done on the Article Processing Charges (APCs) by OA journals which is one among the central mechanisms for funding OA publishing. Solomon & Björk (2012) listed some of the journals indexed in DOAJ charging APCs. A major finding is that professionally published journals charge more than journals published by universities, researchers or societies. However these APCs are generally much lower than the charges required for subscription based publications. Solomon & Björk (2012) conducted another study on the scientific impact of OA and subscription-based journal articles. For this, the articles listed from both DOAJ and Web of Science were downloaded. Interesting results were obtained from this study and it clearly inform us that OA journals do achieve the same scientific impact and quality when compared to that of journal articles published in subscription based platforms. Moreover the chance for getting citation count is comparatively high for OA journal articles. This idea was illustrated by Solomon (2013) in his paper which analyses citation count rate of OA journals listed in Scopus in between 1999 to 2010.

3. Objectives

The main objectives of the study are formulated as follows:

- To find out the OA journals having substantial coverage of the topic Epidemiology and to compile a list.
- To identify the sponsoring agencies /publishers of the OA journals in Epidemiology and to assess their relative productivity.
- To study the country-wise distribution of the OA journals in Epidemiology.
- To examine the language-wise distribution of OA journals in the field of Epidemiology.
- To know about the kind of peer review followed in the OA journals in Epidemiology

4. Methodology

The data for the study were collected from the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). A search in the journals database of DOAJ giving "Epidemiology" as the search term retrieved 180 titles. Details such as sponsoring body, country of publication, language(s), peer review policy, and date of addition of the journal to the DOAJ database were gathered from the database as well as from the sites of the respective journals. The collected data were further analysed based on the objectives of the study. Microsoft excel was used for further analysis and tabulation.

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Growth of Epidemiology journals in DOAJ

Over the years, the number of OA journals in the field of Epidemiology goes on increasing and every year DOAJ updates its database with newly added journals. Table 1 depicts the number

of journals added in each year starting from 2004 along with cumulative number and annual growth rate. An increase in the annual addition is seen since 2013, with the exception of 2014. The number exceeds 20 from 2017 onwards. Annual growth rate is in the range of 10% to 57%. The average of annual growth rate is estimated as 27.6%.

5.2 List of OA Journals in Epidemiology

A list of journals in the field of Epidemiology is obtained from the DOAJ, and an alphabetically arranged list has been compiled. Table 2 gives the list of those journals along with their respective sponsoring / publishing bodies. Titles of all the 180 journals identified as having substantial coverage of papers in epidemiology are included in the list. Further analysis based on their language, country of origin and sponsoring / publishing bodies is attempted in subsequent sections.

Table 1: Year-wise Addition of Journals in Epidemiology to DOAJ Database

Year	Number of Journals Added	Cumulative Number of Journals	Annual Growth Rate
2004	5	5	
2005	2	7	40%
2007	4	11	57.14%
2008	5	16	45.45%
2009	4	20	25%
2010	5	25	25%
2011	5	30	20%
2012	6	36	20%
2013	14	50	38.89%
2014	5	55	10%
2015	13	68	23.64%
2016	18	86	26.47%
2017	22	102	25.58%
2018	23	131	22.55%
2019	23	154	17.56%
2020	26	180	16.88%
Total	180		

Table 2: List of Epidemiology Journals Included in the DOAJ

Sl. No	Name of the Journal	Sponsoring body / Publisher
1	Acta Odontológica Colombiana	Universidad Nacional de Colombia
2	Acta Toxicológica Argentina	Asociación Toxicológica Argentina
3	Actual Infectology	Publishing House Zaslavsky
4	African Journal of Laboratory Medicine/ AJLM	AOSIS
5	AIMS Molecular Science	AIMS Press
6	Anali Meènikivs'kogo Institutu immunology	Mechnikov Institute of Microbiology and
7	Artery Research	Atlantis Press
8	Asia Pacific Journal of Medical Toxicology	Mashhad University of Medical Sciences
9	Asian Journal of Urology	Elsevier
10	Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
11	Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health	Wiley
12	Biomonitoring	De Gruyter
13	BIOpreparations: Prevention, Diagnosis, Treatment	Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation. Federal State Budgetary Institution
14	Brazilian Journal of Epidemiology	Associação Brasileira de Pós-Graduação em Saúde Coletiva
15	Bulgarian Cardiology	Pensoft Publishers
16	Canada Communicable Disease Report	Public Health Agency of Canada
17	Canadian Journal of Pain	Taylor & Francis Group
18	Cancer Biology & Medicine	China Anti-Cancer Association
19	Cancer Communications	Wiley
20	Cancer Management and Research	Dove Medical Press
21	Canine Genetics and Epidemiology	BMC
22	Caspian Journal of Health Research	Guilan University of Medical Sciences
23	Children	MDPI AG
24	Chinese Journal of Lung Cancer Antituberculosis Association	Chinese Anti-Cancer Association; Chinese
25	Clinical Epidemiology	Dove Medical Press
26	Clinical Microbiology and Antimicrobial Chemotherapy	Interregional Association for Clinical Microbiology and Antimicrobial Chemotherapy

Table 2 continued..

27	Clinics in Orthopedic Surgery	Korean Orthopaedic Association
28	Dental journal of Hamadan University of Medical Sciences/Avicenna Journal of Dental Research	Hamadan University of Medical Sciences
29	Duazary /Facultad de Ciencias de la Salud	Universidad del Magdalena
30	ecancermedicalscience/ecancer	ecancer Global Foundation
31	EJC Supplements	Elsevier
32	Electronic Physician	Electronic Physician
33	Emerging Themes in Epidemiology	BMC
34	Environmental Epidemiology	Wolters Kluwer
35	Environmental Health and Toxicology and Toxicology	Korean Society of Environmental Health and Toxicology
36	Epidemiologia e Serviços de Saúde	Ministério da Saúde do Brasil
37	Epidemiology and Health	Korean Society of Epidemiology
38	Epidemiology and Infection	Cambridge University Press
39	Epidemiology and Psychiatric Sciences	Cambridge University Press
40	Epidemiology and Vaccinal Prevention	Numikom LLC
41	Epidemiology Biostatistics and Public Health	PrexS.r.l.
42	Eskişehir Türk Dünyası Uygulamalı Araştırma Merkezi Halk Sağlığı Dergisi	Eskişehir Osmangazi University
43	European Clinical Respiratory Journal	Taylor & Francis Group
44	Eurosurveillance	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
45	Food and Waterborne Parasitology	Elsevier
46	Frontiers in Public Health	Frontiers Media S.A.
47	Gaceta Sanitaria	Elsevier
48	Galicia Clínica	Sociedade Galega de Medicina Interna
49	Gastrointestinal Disorders	MDPI AG
50	Genes and Environment	BMC
51	Global Biosecurity	University of New South Wales
52	Global Epidemiology	Elsevier
53	Global Health, Epidemiology and Genomics	Cambridge University Press
54	GMS Medizinische Informatik, Biometrie und Epidemiologie	German Medical Science GMS Publishing House
55	Hamadan Medical Journal/ HMJ	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
56	Health Promotion and Chronic Disease Prevention in Canada	Public Health Agency of Canada

Table 2 continued..

57	Health Services Research & Managerial Epidemiology	SAGE Publishing
58	Healthline	Indian Association of Preventive and Social Medicine
59	Helminthologia	Sciendo
60	Historical Life Course Studies	International Institute of Social History
61	Hygeia : Revista Brasileira de Geografia Médica e da Saúde	Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
62	Il Giornale di AMD	Idelson Gnocchi
63	Indian Journal of Community Medicine	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
64	Indian Journal of Public Health	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
65	Indonesian Journal of Dental Medicine	Faculty of Dental Medicine, Universitas Airlangga
66	Indonesian Journal of Tropical and Infectious Disease	Universitas Airlangga
67	Infection Ecology & Epidemiology	Taylor & Francis Group
68	Infection Epidemiology and Medicine	University of Tarbiat Modares
69	Injury Epidemiology	BMC
70	International Archives of Health Sciences	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
71	International Archives of Medicine	International Medical Society
72	International Journal of Alcohol and Drug Research/IJADR	The Kettil Bruun Society for Social and Epidemiological Research on Alcohol
73	International Journal of Cardiovascular Sciences	Sociedade Brasileira de Cardiologia
74	International Journal of Dermatology and Venerology	Wolters Kluwer Health
75	International Journal of General Medicine	Dove Medical Press
76	International Journal of Health Policy and Management	Kerman University of Medical Sciences
77	International Journal of Infectious Diseases	Elsevier
78	International Journal of Methods in Psychiatric Research	Wiley
79	International Journal of Mycobacteriology	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
80	International Journal of Noncommunicable Diseases	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
81	International Journal of Veterinary Science and Medicine	Taylor & Francis Group

Table 2 continued..

82	Iranian Journal of Health, Safety and Environment /IJHSE	Iranian Journal of Health, Safety and Environment
83	Iranian Journal of Medical Microbiology	Iranian Society of Microbiology
84	Iranian Journal of Public Health	Tehran University of Medical Sciences
85	JKMA: (JurnalKesehatanMasyarakat Andalas) (Andalas Journal of Public Health)	Andalas University
86	JNCI Cancer Spectrum	Oxford University Press
87	Jorjani Biomedicine Journal	Golestan University of Medical Sciences
88	Journal Infectology	Journal Infectology
89	Journal of Analytical Research in Clinical Medicine	Tabriz University of Medical Sciences
90	Journal of Arthropod-Borne Diseases	Tehran University of Medical Sciences
91	Journal of Biological Dynamics	Taylor & Francis Group
92	Journal of Biostatistics and Epidemiology	Tehran University of Medical Sciences
93	Journal of Cancer and Allied Specialties/ JCAS	ShaukatKhanum Memorial Cancer Hospital & Research Centre
94	Journal of Cancer Epidemiology	Hindawi Limited
95	Journal of Carcinogenesis	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
96	Journal of Congenital Cardiology	BMC
97	Journal of Disease Vector	BadanPenelitiandanPengembangan Kesehatan
98	Journal of Enam Medical College	Enam Medical College, Dhaka
99	Journal of Epidemiology and Global Health	Atlantis Press
100	Journal of Epidemiology and Public Health	Masters Program in Public Health, UniversitasSebelasMaret
101	Journal of Epidemiology	Japan Epidemiological Association
102	Journal of Health Promotion and Behavior	Masters Program in Public Health, UniversitasSebelasMaret
103	Journal of High Institute of Public Health	Alexandria University
104	Journal of Infection and Public Health	Elsevier
105	Journal of Infection in Developing Countries/ JIDC	The Journal of Infection in Developing Countries
106	Journal of Jiroft University of Medical Sciences	Jiroft University of Medical Sciences
107	Journal of Medical Bacteriology	Tehran University of Medical Sciences
108	Journal of Microbiology, Epidemiology and Immunobiology	Central Research Institute for Epidemiology
109	Journal of Obesity & Metabolic Syndrome	Korean Society for the Study of Obesity

Table 2 continued..

110	Journal of Occupational Health	Wiley
111	Journal of Oral Health and Oral Epidemiology	Kerman University of Medical Sciences
112	Journal of Oral Microbiology	Taylor & Francis Group
113	Journal of Preventive Epidemiology	Society of Diabetic Nephropathy Prevention
114	Journal of Preventive Medicine and Public Health	Korean Society for Preventive Medicine
115	Journal of Public Health Research /JPHR	PAGEPress Publications
116	Journal of Research in Pharmacy Practice	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
117	Journal of the Egyptian Public Health Association	SpringerOpen
118	Journal of the International Association of Providers of AIDS Care	SAGE Publishing
119	JRSM Cardiovascular Disease	SAGE Publishing
120	Jurnal Berkala Epidemiologi	Universitas Airlangga
121	Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan Masyarakat /JIKM	Faculty of Public Health, Sriwijaya University
122	Jurnal Kesehatan Komunitas (Journal of Community Health)/KesKom	STIKes Hang Tuah Pekanbaru
123	Letters in Biomathematics	Intercollegiate Biomathematics Alliance
124	Lifestyle Genomics	Karger Publishers
125	Medicina (Buenos Aires)	Fundación Revista Medicina
126	Mediterranean Journal of Infection, Microbes and Antimicrobials	Galenos Yayinevi
127	Mersin University Journal of Medical Science	Mersin University
128	Microbial Genomics	Microbiology Society
129	Middle East Journal of Cancer/MEJC	Shiraz University of Medical Sciences
130	Norsk Epidemiologi /Norwegian Journal of Epidemiology	Norsk Forening for Epidemiologi
131	Obesity Facts	Karger Publishers
132	Open Respiratory Archives	Elsevier
133	Orthopaedic Journal of Sports Medicine	SAGE Publishing
134	Papillomavirus Research	Elsevier
135	Parasite	EDP Sciences
136	Parasite Epidemiology and Control	Elsevier
137	Payesh /Health Monitor	Iranian Institute for Health Sciences Research
138	Perspectives In Medical Research	Prathima Institute of Medical Sciences

Table 2 continued..

139	Polish Journal of Public Health	Sciendo
140	Problems of Particularly Dangerous Infections	Federal Government Health Institution, Russian Research Anti-Plague Institute "Microbe"
141	Proceedings of Singapore Healthcare	SAGE Publishing
142	Promotion de la santé et prévention des maladies chroniques au Canada	Agence de la santé publique du Canada
143	Psoriasis : Targets and Therapy	Dove Medical Press
144	Public Health in Practice	Elsevier
145	Public Health Perspective Journal	UniversitasNegeri Semarang
146	Respiratory Medicine: X	Elsevier
147	Revista Argentina de Microbiología	Elsevier España
148	Revista Argentina de SaludPública	Ministerio de Salud
149	RevistaChilena de SaludPública	Universidad de Chile
150	RevistaCubana de Higiene y Epidemiología	Editorial CienciasMédicas
151	Revista de Epidemiologia e Controle de Infecção	Universidade de Santa Cruz do Sul
152	Revista de SaludAmbiental	Sociedad Española de SanidadAmbiental
153	Revista de SaludPública del Paraguay	InstitutoNacional de Salud (INS)
154	Revista de SaludPública	Universidad Nacional de Córdoba
155	Revista de SaúdePública do Paraná	Secretaria de Estado da Saúde do Paraná
156	RevistaMadrileña de SaludPública/ REMASP Madrid	Dirección General de SaludPública. Consejería de Sanidad. Comunidad de
157	RevistaVenezolana de SaludPública	Universidad CentrocidentalLisandro Alvarado
158	SaludColectiva Nacional de Lanús	Instituto de SaludColectiva, Universidad
159	SaludPública de México	InstitutoNacional de SaludPública
160	São Paulo Medical Journal	AssociaçãoPaulista de Medicina
161	Saudi Dental Journal	Elsevier
162	Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences	Elsevier
163	Scandinavian Journal of Primary Health Care	Taylor & Francis Group
164	Siberian Journal of Oncology	Tomsk National Research Medical Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences
165	Slovenskapediatrija Disorders	The Society for Children with Metabolic
166	Southern African Journal of Infectious Diseases	AOSIS

Table 2 continued..

167	SSM: Population Health	Elsevier
168	The Indonesian Journal of Public Health	UniversitasAirlangga
169	The Medical Journal of Basrah University	University of Basrah
170	The Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications
171	The University of Louisville Journal of Respiratory Infections	University of Louisville
172	Tropical Medicine and Health	BMC
173	Turkish Journal of Public Health	Turkish Society of Public Health Specialists
174	Unnes Journal of Public Health	UniversitasNegeri Semarang
175	VacciMonitor	Finlay Ediciones
176	Veterinary and Animal Science	Elsevier
177	Veterinary Research	BMC
178	Virus Evolution	Oxford University Press
179	Western Pacific Surveillance and Response/ WPSAR	World Health Organization
180	ZhongliuFangzhiYanjiu /Cancer Research on Prevention and Treatment	Magazine House of Cancer Research on Prevention and Treatment

5.3 Language of Journals

OA journals in Epidemiology covered in DOAJ bring out their content in one or more of the 16 different languages listed in table 3. The major portion, 149 journals (68.03 %) are in English; and Spanish being second with 21 (9.58 %) titles. The

third position goes to Portuguese with 10 (4.56 %) journals; and it is followed by Russian. Some of the journals are multilingual in the sense that they publish papers in two or more languages. Hence there is data overlap in the numbers and percentage.

Table 3: Language-wise Distribution of Journals

Sl. No	Language	Number of Journals	Percentage
1	English	149	68.03
2	Spanish	21	9.58
3	Portuguese	10	4.56
4	Russian	9	4.10
5	Indonesian	8	3.65
6	French	4	1.82
7	Turkish	4	1.82
8	Chinese	3	1.36
9	Persian	3	1.36
10	Ukrainian	2	0.91
11	Bulgarian	1	0.45
12	Galician	1	0.45
13	German	1	0.45
14	Italian	1	0.45
15	Norwegian	1	0.45
16	Slovenian	1	0.45

5.4 Publisher-wise Distribution

It is identified that the 180 journals with substantial coverage of learned contributions in Epidemiology covered in the DOAJ are either sponsored or published by 115 organisations. Out of these, Elsevier tops the list with 17 journals of their own, and Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications is in the second position publishing 10 journals. BMC and Taylor & Francis Group share the third position publishing seven OA journals each. The top 10 major publishers are listed in the Table 4.

Table 4: Top Ranked Publishers

Sl. No	Publishers	No. of Journals
1	Elsevier	17
2	Wolters Kluwer Medknow Publications	10
3	BMC	7
4	Taylor & Francis Group	7
5	SAGE Publishing	5
6	Dove Medical Press	4
7	Tehran University of Medical Sciences	4
8	Wiley	4
9	Cambridge University Press	3
10	Universitas Airlangga	3

5.5 Geographical Distribution of Publishers

The 180 journals referred to above originate from 39 countries of the world. As it is evident from table 5 and the accompanying graphical presentation (Figure 1) United Kingdom has the highest number (34) of titles which forms 18.88 % of the total. The second place goes to Iran with 19 (10.55 %) journals published, and the third place is for United States (US) with 13 (7.22 %) journals. Half of the total number of journals belongs to five top ranking nations namely, UK, Iran, USA, India and Indonesia.

Table 5: Country-wise Distribution of Publishers

Sl. No	Country	No. of Journals	Percentage
1	United Kingdom	34	18.88
2	Iran, Islamic Republic of	19	10.55
3	United States	13	7.22
4	India	12	6.66
5	Indonesia	12	6.66
6	Netherlands	8	4.44
7	Brazil	7	3.88
8	Russian Federation	7	3.88
9	Spain	6	3.33
10	Argentina	5	2.77
11	Korea, Republic of	5	2.77
12	Switzerland	5	2.77
13	Canada	4	2.22
14	Italy	4	2.22
15	Turkey	4	2.22

Figure 1: Geographical Distribution of Publishers

5.6 Peer Review Type

Learned journals have been using different types of peer reviewing to accept papers for publication. The three types often used are single blind, double blind and open peer review. In single blind type, author does not know the identity of the reviewer, but the reviewer knows the identity of the author. In double blind type neither the author nor the reviewer knows each other. In open peer review the identity of author and reviewer are transparent to all concerned. More recently other models such as transparent peer review, collaborative peer review and post publication peer review have also been attempted. In transparent peer review, the review report is posted along with the published paper, with or without the identity of the reviewer. Collaborative peer review consists of generating a unified review report with the collaboration of two or more reviewers or the author himself revising the paper under the supervision of the reviewer. Post publication review entrusts the author to revise the paper even after its publication.

The type of peer review followed by the journals under consideration varies. Nearly half (48%) of the journals follow double-blind peer review (Table 6). Sixty one (34 %) journals follow blind peer review and 31 (17 %) follow other forms of peer review and only one journal follows open peer review.

Table 6: Distribution of journals by Peer review process followed

SI. No.	Type of Review	Number of Journals	Percentage
1	Single blind	61	34
2	Double blind	87	48
3	Open peer review	1	1
4	Others / unknown	31	17

6. Conclusion

OA movement in scholarly publishing is very much useful for the academic community as well as the society at large. Epidemiology, the science dealing with public health has to have more and more OA journals all over the world. From the search in DOAJ, 180 OA journals could be identified in this subject field and it is considerably a good number. Though scholarly papers in 16 languages are included in these journals, more than two third are in English language (68%) which was an expected result. Spanish (9.5 %) and Portuguese (4.5%) languages also produce significant amount of research output. Out of thirty-nine countries from which the 180 journals under study are published, the UK came first with thirty-four journals (18.8 %). Iran and USA are the second and third with nineteen and thirteen journals respectively. India is in fourth position with twelve (6.6 %) journals being published. Different peer review methods are used among these OA journals. Majority of journals (61 journals) follows double blind peer review method. This indicates that OA journals are not making compromises in review, which in turn ensure quality in scholarly output. It is also concluded that like any other fields, OA journals are increasing in number in the field of Epidemiology. These are all positive indicators since any development in the field of Epidemiology will directly benefit the health status of a society.

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